

Role of Finance Commission in Shaping Financial Structure of India: A Constitutional Perspective

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Abstract

Finances play an important role in federal-provincial relations. In any federal arrangement, the framers of the Constitution have a delicate and difficult task to maintain resource expenditure harmony at all levels of government. In reality, a perfect match between spending and resources is practically impossible to achieve, since expenditures and resources are asymmetric. Inconsistency can be seen in all federal systems, though to varying degrees. The Australian Commonwealth Grants Commission prompted the establishment of the Finance Commission. In India, however, the Finance Commission, which has a wide range of responsibilities, is not a permanent body; it meets only once every five years, and its duties are completed once the report is published. The President of India distributes and distributes the net revenues of taxes to be split between the Centre and the States, provides grants in aid to the States' revenue, and other items related to the Fiscal Federal system, on the recommendation of the Finance Commission. Each chamber of Parliament receives the Finance Commission's recommendations, along with an explanatory memorandum. In light of current financial conditions, the authors of this paper will look at the mismatch between resources and liabilities. The author of this article discusses constitutional provisions concerning Centre-State Financial Relations, with an emphasis on the Union's and States' expenditure responsibilities, resources assigned to the Union and States, and the role of the Finance Commission in Fiscal Federalism.

Keywords: Finance, Fiscal Federalism, Finance Commission, Centre-State Financial Relationships.

1. Introduction

Finance is the lifeblood of any organization's day-to-day operations. Both the federal and state governments have taxing authority when it comes to revenue generation. The revenue generated by taxes collected is insufficient to support efficient state government operations. As a result, in order to maintain a level of creation equilibrium, the Constitution provides for a variety of revenue sources. The Indian Constitution expressly allows for revenue distribution between the Centre and the States by permitting a percentage of the Centre's earnings to be transferred to the States through tax sharing. To grasp the concept of Federalism, let us go back to the very first foundation stone. Federalism in administrative

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elements can be traced back to the Mughal dynasty, particularly Sher Shah's land revenue system, and took shape during Akbar's reign, when he divided his empire into 12 provinces, according to historians such as P. Spear. During the mughal period, it has been hypothesised that there was a swing between strong centre and local. The Morley Minto Reforms failed to bring India closer to parliamentary rule. In 1917, the British government issued a statement encouraging Indians to participate in administration. The Constitution of India, 1950, Part XII Chapter 3 deals with the financial relationship between the Union and the States, as well as other financial issues. The Union Government has the authority to tax matters covered by the Union list; the State Government has the authority to tax matters covered by the State list; and because there is no concurrent list provision, residuary matters are dealt with by the Union list.

The Finance Commission, which is empowered to offer recommendations under Article 281 of the Indian Constitution, plays a crucial role in the Union-State financial interaction. Furthermore, Article 280 of the Constitution mandates that the President appoint a Finance Commission every five years from the date of its establishment. The Finance Commission has the authority to make recommendations to the President on the following matters:

- i. Distribution of revenue earned (by the way of taxes) between Centre and State Government
- ii. Grants-in-aids from Consolidated fund of India to States
- iii. Or any other financial matter to the Commission by the President.

There are particular ways in which Union government collects taxes. Those can be broadly divided under four heads (Article 268-270)

- i. Duty charged by Union but collected by States
- ii. Service tax charged by Union but collected both by Union as well as States.
- iii. Taxes charged as well as collected by the Union government but distributed amongst the States and
- iv. Taxes charged and distributed amongst Union and States.

There have been numerous instances in India's financial framework where there has been disagreement over tax allocation. In this issue, there was a disagreement over whether the Union or the States had the authority to levy taxes. A narrower interpretation was given in *Union of India v. H.S Dhillon*² when the matter came up before the Supreme Court. But later on, this judgment was overruled in *ITC v. State of Haryana*³ and it was held that matters under both the list will be given wider interpretation. Matters relating to subject under a particular list will be taxed by the same authority and not by the Union as a power to tax on residuary matter.

Exemption of property from tax

² AIR 1972 SC 1061

³ AIR 1981 SC 774

The property and income of states is exempted from the taxes of Union under Article 289. Further the States cannot impose tax on water or electricity used by Union under Article 288. By looking closely into the financial relation between the Union and State government it is very clear that States are empowered to levied tax on the matters contained under the State list thus states are not at all subordinate to the Union for revenue. Only Union government provides for additional revenue as well it acts as a life saver in cases of scarcity of funds by giving loans and grants to states.

In order to understand the role of Finance Commission in respect of Centre-State financial relationship we need to examine the scheme followed by it since its Constitution. There have been thirteen finance commission constituted since its creation. There are as follows-

I. First Finance Commission⁴:

The First Finance Commission was constituted on 20 November 1951, under the chairmanship of Mr. K.C. Neogy. In practice no particular terms of reference were spelt out so it has decided its own functions in terms of the provisions of Article 280 of the Constitution. The First Finance Commission reviewed the evolution of Centre-state relationship leading to the relevant provisions in the Constitution. It was now the responsibility of the states to focus on the development and welfare of its citizen. This is further supplemented by the additional revenue supply from centre. But such supplementation was subjected to a certain conditions attached. Those conditions were-

- i. revenue generation power of centre and
- ii. given after the needs of centre were being satisfied.

The First Finance Commission had laid down two major principles that were followed by the subsequent Commissions. The principles are:

- i. while distribution of revenues between different states, principle of uniformity must be followed in case of the determination of grants-in-aid; and
- ii. the aim of distribution of revenue shall focus on curbing the problem inequalities between the different States.

II. Second Finance Commission⁵

The Second Finance Commission was constituted on 1 June 1956 under the chairmanship of Shri K. Santhanam In order to supplement the two principles laid down by the First Finance Commission, an equally important third principle was laid down by the Second Finance Commission. The third principle stated that “on a balance between devolution by transfer of shares of taxes and devolution by fixed grant-in-aid. The sharing of tax was done with the motive to fulfill the gaps between the revenue earned and expenses incurred. Further according to the commission the purpose of Grants-in-aid should be largely be of residuary type and must be given a broader perspective.”

III. Third Finance Commission⁶

⁴ <https://fincomindia.nic.in/>

⁵ Ibid.

⁶ Ibid.

The Third Finance Commission was appointed in 1960, chaired by Shri A.K. Chanda and the its other members. The Commission was appointed to give recommendations to the president in respect of

- i. Tax Sharing between the Centre and the State and allocation of Income Tax and Central Excise Duties
- ii. To provide financial assistance by way of Grants-in-Aid to states.

IV. Fourth Finance Commission⁷

The Fourth Finance Commission was constituted on 18 May 1964, under the chairmanship of Dr. P.V. Rajamannar, the Commission broadened its own scope. It observed that “there is no distinction between plan and non-plan expenditure in the Constitution. Further the capital expenditure is also falls within the scope of the Finance Commission. On one hand it supported the view of third finance commission by stating that finance commission cannot ‘fill-up non-plan revenue deficits reported by the states’. On the other it differed from the view of the Third Commission that ‘the relative financial weaknesses of the states’ should be the marked as a criterion for determining the shares of states in the divisible pool.” Dr. P.V. Rajamannar, the Chairman of the Fourth Finance Commission, is correct in pointing out the Finance Commission's advising role throughout his period of office. Because the Finance Commission is anticipated to be quasi-judicial, the government should not reject its recommendations unless there are "extremely strong reasons" for doing so, according to him. The role of the Finance Commission in India's fiscal federalism is critical to its advising duty. In the past, the roles of the Finance Commission and the Planning Commission overlapped. The creation of NITI Aayog has eliminated any possibility of this causing confusion within either organisation.

V. Fifth Finance Commission⁸

The Fifth Finance Commission constituted in on 15 March 1968, was of the view that the revenue deficits of states shall be met by the states by raising the finance from different resources. However, this will not be a principle which will be followed as it is difficult for any outside authority to judge the policies of the states in respect of taxation, expenditure and investment. The commission came across with a problem that the existing levels of taxations both at the Centre as well as states were not adequately to meet their expenses. The Fifth Finance Commission in India is also responsible for enforcing Article 275's grants-in-aid restrictions. This money comes from the Consolidated Fund of India, and it's given to states that are truly in need of financial aid. Role played by the Fifth Finance Commission in India:

- The fifth finance commission recommends the division of the net proceeds of various taxes between the federal government and the individual states. Clause (1) of Article 275 specifies that it governs the issue of grants-in-aid for states that are in need of financial help. States in India receive the funds as a means of bolstering their tax bases.
- The additional estate duty for property that does not comprise agricultural lands will be changed by the fifth finance commission.

⁷ <https://fincomindia.nic.in/>

⁸ Ibid.

- Additional charges on cotton fabrics, sugar, tobacco, woollen fabrics, silk fabrics, and rayon or artificial silk fabrics are also under the purview of India's fifth finance commission

VI. Sixth Finance Commission⁹

The Sixth Finance Commission was constituted in 1973 under the chairmanship of Shri K. Brahmananda Reddi. The Commission felt that the provisions of the Constitution relating to Union-state financial relationship had been framed with due care and diligence to meet the demands of changing society. And if there are strains and stress in the society will be curbed by a scheme under which decisions regarding revenue will be taken after the widest possible measure of consultations. With the evolution of concept of economic planning, the commission has acquired a position in developmental activities, cutting across the Constitutional delimitation of powers under the Constitution. As per the scheme of commission devolution meant that the resources are for the development of nation and must reach to places were required the most. The Sixth Finance Commission adheres to the Constitution of India's Chapter-I of portion XII. State governments who require financial assistance to boost their tax revenues are governed by it as well. Sixth Finance Commission's concerns as:

- (a) As per Chapter I of part XII of the Constitution of India, to offer suggestions for the division of the net profits of taxes between the Union and the states.
- (b) For the states that need financial aid under Article 275, to provide suggestions on the rules governing grants-in-aid. The Consolidated Fund of India provides the funding for all of them.
- (c) The equitable distribution of taxes among India's several states is the responsibility of the sixth finance commission.
- (d) It is the responsibility of the sixth finance commission to ensure that any required amendments are made to the taxation of the net proceeds of estate duty in terms of property that does not include agricultural land.
- (e) The Additional Duties of Excise (Goods of Special Importance) Act, 1957 imposes additional excise duties on a variety of goods, including cotton fabrics, woollen fabrics, silk fabrics, tobacco, sugar, and rayon or artificial silk fabrics, which the sixth finance commission keeps.
- (f) The replacement of sales tax for the aforementioned goods is the focus of the sixth finance commission.

VII. Seventh Finance Commission.¹⁰

The Seventh Finance Commission was constituted in 1978 under the chairmanship of Shri J.M. Shelat. The major recommendation of the commission was regarding increasing the share of the net proceeds to be shared with states. Among other things, the seventh finance commission recommends changes to the net proceeds of taxes and additional duties,

⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰ <https://fincomindia.nic.in/>

modifications to the rules governing the net proceeds of additional excise duties levied on various commodities, and consideration of the grants in aid that are available for the tax levied on the fare for railway passengers.

The 7th Finance Commission's primary responsibilities

- (a) Section XII of the Indian Constitution specifies how net tax revenues should be distributed between the Union and the various states, and this chapter makes recommendations in this regard.
- (b) It gives recommendations for the grants-in-aid for the states who seek financial support to boost the income and these financial aids comes from the Consolidated Fund of India
- (c) The commission also has the authority to propose adjustments to net proceeds and extra responsibilities for property other than agricultural land.
- (d) Sugar, tobacco, cotton fabrics, woollen fabrics, rayon fabrics, and artificial silk fabrics all have their supplementary duties adjusted as a result of this.
- (e) The commission is also responsible for the fiscal management systems in the states.
- (f) It also ensures that investments in irrigation and power projects, transportation plans, and commercial and industrial organisations will return at an acceptable rate.
- (g) State plans for supporting relief expenditures are also examined by the committee. It assesses the five-year plan's non-plan capital shortfall for Indian states.

VIII. Eight Finance Commission¹¹

The Eight Finance commission was constituted in 1984 under the chairmanship of Shri Y.B. Chavan. The Commission followed the same scheme followed by the previous commission in respect of sharing of tax and grant-in-aids. The major objective of the Eighth Finance Commission was to reduce interstate disparities through their scheme of devolution. The Eighth Finance Commission's main areas of concern in India:

- (a) In accordance with Chapter I of Part XII of the Indian Constitution, the eighth finance commission offers recommendations for the distribution of net tax proceeds within the Union and among the Indian states.
- (b) An additional duty of the commission is to make suggestions on how various Indian states can raise their tax collections through grants in aid. In accordance with Article 275 of the Indian Constitution, these funds are provided by the Consolidated Fund of India.
- (c) For example, the commission may recommend modifications to the net profits of estate duty in terms of property and increased excise charges on cotton fabrics, woollen fabrics, sugar and tobacco.
- (d) Additionally, it is in charge of revising the taxes levied on rail passengers that were eliminated.
- (e) There is a committee that looks into how emergency aid is paid for. Non-plan capital gaps can also be evaluated using this tool.

IX. Ninth Finance Commission¹²

¹¹ Ibid.

The Ninth Finance Commission was constituted in June 1987 under the chairmanship of Mr. N.K.P Salve. The Commission was asked to give recommendations as to changing the principles that govern the distribution of net proceeds of central taxes between the union and the states. The Commission recommended that “85% of the divisible pool of the income tax shall be assigned to the state and out of the net distributable proceeds a sum equal to 1.437% should be deemed to represent the proceeds attributable to the union territories. The loans given to the federal states for drought relief during 1986– 89 as outstanding on 31 March 1989 are to be waived.” Aside from proposing adjustments if necessary to the regulations controlling net revenues of estate taxes and additional excise charges on commodities, as well as assessing states' financial conditions in terms of debt returns, the commission is responsible for financing relief fund expenditure in various state.

The India's Ninth Finance Commission's Responsibilities

- (a) According to Chapter I of Part XII, the Constitution of India, the ninth finance commission recommends that the Union and the states share the net proceeds of taxes, as well as apportioning portions amongst the states.
- (b) Article 275 of the Indian constitution calls for recommendations on the rules governing the grants-in-aid system for boosting the economies of the states.
- (c) The commission has the authority to propose any changes to the Additional Duties of Excise (Goods of Special Importance) Act, 1957, and the repealed tax on passengers under the Railway Passenger Fares Tax Act, 1957, if they are necessary.
- (d) It will be used to determine the distribution of taxes in the states based on population data.
- (e) Additionally, the additional excise taxes are used to evaluate whether or not sales tax should be replaced.
- (f) According to their debt positions, states are rated by the commission.
- (g) It also examines the government of India's policies on the financing of state relief expenditures.

X. Tenth Finance Commission¹³

The Tenth Finance Commission was constituted in 1995 under chairmanship of Shri Krishna Chandra Pant. The question before the Commission was regarding the grounds on which the shares of Union Territories are to be determined. The Commission recommended that “share cannot be determined on the same grounds used for determining the share of States. The percentage would be 0.927% for the years 1995–2000. The share of the net proceeds would be 77.5% for five years. The distribution of the net proceeds among states would be as 20% on the basis of population, 60% on basis the of distance of per capita income, 5% on the basis of area adjusted, 5% on basis of infrastructure index and 10% on the basis of tax effort.” The Tenth Finance Commission is also involved in suggesting changes to the net proceeds in terms of additional excise duties on goods under the Additional Duties of Excise (Goods of Special Importance) Act, 1957 in place of sales tax and the repealed tax on railway passengers, evaluating the population factor for degeneration of taxes, duties, and grants-in-

¹² Ibid.

¹³ <https://fincomindia.nic.in/>

aid in the states, and finally the commission is involved in the commutation of the tenth state budgets to the federal budget. The Tenth Financial Commission's Initiatives:

- (a) The Tenth Commission recommends that the net profits of taxes should be distributed between the Union and the states in accordance with Chapter I of Part XII of the Constitution of India, as well as the allocation of shares within the states.
- (b) According to Article 275 of India's Constitution, India's states are entitled to grants-in-aid, which the commission recommends based on the goal of boosting the state's income.
- (c) Additional excise charges imposed on goods of special importance under the Additional Duties of Excise (Goods of Special Importance) Act, 1957, can be reformed by the tenth finance commission, as a replacement for the sales tax imposed on them by the government previously.
- (d) The Railway Passenger Fares Act, 1957, which imposed a charge on rail passengers, is also amended by the commission.
- (e) Tax and duty distribution proposals are based on population ratios as well. In addition, the panel evaluates the state's financial situation and the Calamity Relief Fund.

XI. Eleventh Finance Commission¹⁴

The Eleventh Finance Commission was constituted on 3 July 1998 under the chairmanship of Prof. A.M. Khusro. The Commission was asked to give recommendations regarding centre-state financial relationship i.e., distribution of the net proceeds of taxes and the allocation between the States of the shares of these proceeds, to formulate principles governing the grants-in-aid given to States out of the Consolidated Fund of India, measures needed to augment the Consolidated Fund of a State to supplement the resources of the Panchayats and Municipalities in the State. Apart from overseeing states' financial health in light of various development plans, the Eleventh Finance Commission of India consults with state finance commissions to make recommendations and makes suggestions regarding rules governing the net proceeds of additional excise. It is also tasked with examining states' financial health in light of those consultations. The Eleventh Finance Commission's responsibilities, Recommendations for tax distribution and laws governing financial aid to states to raise their revenues should be made by this committee.

- (a) Work with the State Finance Commission to develop suggestions for enhancing state funding through the addition of resources from Panchayats and municipalities throughout the state.
- (b) Restructuring public finances to ensure macroeconomic stability • The commission will work with local governments to make recommendations in conjunction with the state finance commission.
- (c) Additional excise levies on commodities and tax-fare handouts for train passengers could be revised as a result of this study. It also assesses the state's financial situation to keep tabs on its debt positions.

¹⁴ Ibid.

- (d) Apart from overseeing states' financial health in light of various development plans, the Eleventh Finance Commission of India consults with state finance commissions to make recommendations and makes suggestions regarding rules governing the net proceeds of additional excise. It is also tasked with examining states' financial health in light of those consultations.
- (e) Recommendations to be made by the 11th Finance Commission on the division of federal and state taxes, as well as the laws governing financial assistance provided to states to help them raise revenue
- (f) Work with the State Finance Commission to develop suggestions for enhancing state funding through the addition of resources from Panchayats and municipalities throughout the state.
- (g) Restructuring public finances to ensure macroeconomic stability • The commission will work with local governments to make recommendations in conjunction with the state finance commission.
- (h) Additional excise levies on commodities and tax-fare handouts for train passengers could be revised as a result of this study.
- (i) It also assesses the state's financial situation to keep tabs on its debt positions.

XII. Twelfth Finance Commission¹⁵

The Twelfth Finance Commission was constituted on 1 November 2002 under the chairmanship of C.Rangrajan, to make recommendations on the distribution of net proceeds of tax to be shared between union and states. The major recommendation of the Commission was that “the share of tax to be given to State was fixed to 30.5%. The total sum total of grant that to be given to panchayati raj institutions and local urban bodies for the period of 2005–09 will be Rs 200 billion & Rs 50 billion respectively. The total non-plan revenue deficit grant of Rs 568.56 billion is recommended to 15 states and the total grant of Rs 10172 is recommended for 8 educationally backward states.”

The activities of the Twelfth Finance Commission of India were-

- (a) In order to make recommendations on how the taxes should be split between the federal government and the individual states,
- (b) Assist states in increasing their tax collections by making advice on grant-related rules.
- (c) Make suggestions for increasing the Consolidated Fund of India, which is distributed among several Indian states.
- (d) To assess the financial health of Indian states and make recommendations for reorganising public finances in order to promote a more stable financial system and macroeconomics
- (e) Taxation levels should be used as a basis for evaluating central government resources allocated to Indian states
- (f) Maintaining the capital assets and non-scheduled expenditures.
- (g) Regarding irrigation projects and power plants as well as other government and public sector organisations, facilities are needed.

¹⁵ Ibid.

- (h) To examine the Fiscal Reform Facility (FRF) created by the federal government to strengthen the state's financial system
- (i) To examine how the National Calamity Contingency Fund and the Calamity Relief Fund handle the funding of calamities. A detailed breakdown of receipts and expenditures at the state level.

XIII. Thirteen Finance Commission¹⁶

The Thirteen Finance Commission was constituted in 2007 under the chairmanship of Shri Vijay Kelkar. The major recommendations of the Commission were “as regarding increasing the share of tax to be shared by Union with States which is 32%, which is 1.5%points higher than the recommendation of 12th Finance Commission. Both Union and states should conclude 'Grand Bargain' to implement the model Goods and Services Act (GST), as an incentive to the states, the commission recommended a sanction of the grant of Rs500 billion.” Although the primary task of the Thirteenth Finance Commission (THFC) was to recommend measures to improve resource sharing, its mandate also required it to investigate ways to combat climate change and environmental sustainability, as well as to assess the impact of a proposed goods and services tax (GST) on central and state finances.

Aside from completing its basic mission of producing objective recommendations on resource sharing in a short time frame of two years, the THFC attempted to address a wide variety of topics within the scope of its Terms of Reference. The THFC's suggestions have the following features.

- (a) An increase from 30.5 percent to 32 percent in the vertical proportion of tax devolution
- (b) An outline for the GST, as well as incentives based on adherence to that outline.
- (c) In order to ensure that the updated fiscal consolidation plan is adhered to, the plan has been linked to transfer payments.
- (d) Allowing a certain percentage of central revenues to be devolved to local governments as grants.
- (e) The ToR calls for a significant number of grants with specific objectives, such combating climate change or ensuring that government spending has a greater impact and yields better results..

XIV. Fourteen Finance Commission¹⁷

The Fourteenth Finance Commission was constituted in 2013 under the chairmanship of Dr. Y.V.Reddy. The commission was of view that tax devolution shall be the principal means for transfer of resources to the States. Further the Commission has divided the grants into two categories: “First for gram panchayats and second for municipal bodies. In furtherance grants are of two types i.e., basic grant and performance. The ration of basic to performance grant is 90:10 for panchayats; and 80:20 for municipalities. Eight centrally sponsored schemes (CSSes) will be delinked from support from the Centre. There are recommendations on

¹⁶ https://fincomindia.nic.in/writereaddata/html_en_files/oldcommission_html/fincom13/index13fc.htm

¹⁷ https://fincomindia.nic.in/writereaddata/html_en_files/oldcommission_html/fincom14/index14fc.htm

cooperative federalism, GST, fiscal consolidation road map, pricing of public utilities and PSUs, too.”

For this commission, we must "review the state of Union and State finances, deficit and debt levels, keeping in mind in particular the fiscal consolidation roadmap recommended by the Thirteenth Finance Commission and suggest measures for maintaining a stable and sustainable fiscal environment consistent with equitable growth," according to the Terms of Reference (ToR)."

XV. Fifteenth Finance Commission

The 15th Finance Commission's report for the period of 2021-22 to 2025-26 was submitted to the President of India on 9 November 2020. There were a few major areas of emphasis in the Commission's findings, including:

- (a) Local government grants and disaster management funds were recommended by the Commission in addition to revenue devolution.
- (b) Second, the Commission was tasked with recommending performance incentives for States in a wide range of critical areas, including the adoption of DBT, solid waste management, and the power sector, among others.
- (c) For the first time in India's history, a separate, and independent, funding system for India's defence and security was requested by the 15th Finance Commission.
- (d) Consequently, the Finance Commission has attempted to safeguard and promote the State's financial autonomy. In addition, attention has been paid to ensuring that States in need receive adequate financial assistance.

Thus we can say that Finance Commission has tried to promote and maintain the autonomy enjoyed by the State in financial matters. Further has focused on providing sufficient finance assistance to States who are in need of it.

Fiscal Federalism in Constitution of India

Certain groups of products are taxed by the Centre but collected by the States, according to Article 268 of the Indian Constitution of 1950. Stamp duties on toilet preparation, for example, are not included in India's consolidated fund. These goods are preserved in the Union list for legislative purposes, but they are used as a source of revenue by the states in practise. Article 268(A)¹⁸ was inserted by the Eighty Eight Constitutional (Amendment) Act 2003.¹⁹ According to this provision the taxes on services are to be levied by the Centre and collected by the Centre government as well as the State government in the ratio prescribed by the President. Further in *All India Federation of Tax practitioners v. Union of India*,²⁰ it was held that it is not true that only State governments have power to collect tax on service and profession. Both the Centre and State shall enjoy jurisdiction on collection of taxes on service by giving it a widest interpretation.²¹ There are two clauses in Article 269²²

¹⁸ Article 268 of the Constitution of India, 1950

¹⁹ <http://indiacode.nic.in/coiweb/amend/amend88.htm>

²⁰ AIR 2007 SC 2990

²¹ Ibid.

²² Article 269 of the Constitution of India, 1950

substituted by the Eighty Constitutional (Amendment) Act 2000. According to Clause (1) of the current provision, the Centre will levy and collect a tax on the sale, purchase, and consignment of commodities, which will be allotted to states in accordance with the law of parliament. Newspaper is not included in the definition of Sale and Purchase of Goods. Clause (2) goes on to say that the net proceeds received in any financial year, excluding those that go into the consolidated fund of India, will be dispersed among the states in accordance with the statute of parliament. States will be given 29 percent of total income from taxes and duties, subject to the revision.²³ The Eighty Constitutional (Amendment) Act 2000 replaces Article 270²⁴, which states that taxes and duties under the Union List, except those provided under Article 268,268-A,269, shall be levied and collected by the Union, but distributed between the Union and States in a manner determined by the President after consultation with the Finance Commission. "The income tax attributable to Union territory forms a part of the Consolidated Fund of India," the Supreme Court ruled in *T.M. Kannian v. I.T.O.*²⁵ It is not essential to issue any income tax distributions with respect to Union territories because those territories are handled centrally by the President."²⁶ According to Article 271²⁷ the Parliament by law may increase or decrease surcharge on duties and taxes which is not to be distributed forming part of consolidated fund of India. The Article 276²⁸ empowers the State to levie and collect tax on trade, profession, calling and employment. These taxes are collected to be used by the State, municipalities and local bodies. In *All India Tax practitioners v. Union of India*²⁹ The issue was with regard to legislative competency of Union to levy tax on Chartered accountant. The appeal was dismissed and the Supreme Court defined the term services as the services are broadly classified as Performance service i.e., practising chartered accountants, travel agent etc and Property based services i.e., architects, engineers etc.

Grants-in-AID

Other than the source of finance, the Union of India provides for certain grants to States. Grant is basically transfers of resource from Union to State. Under the Constitution of India grants are discussed in following provisions:

1. Grants in lieu Article 273 of the Constitution of India

Earlier in the Government of India Act, there was a provision regarding sharing of net proceeds of jute export duty by the centre with its provinces. But there is no as such provision in the Constitution of India. As per Article 273 from the period of 10 years from the commencement of the Constitution, the jute growing states of West Bengal, Bihar, Orissa and Assam will receive grants-in-aid from the Union in lieu of the above share of the jute export duty. Grants in lieu of export duty on jute and jute products are dealt with under Article 273. It also states that in lieu of assigning any share of the net proceeds of export duty on jute and

²³ Narendra kumar, "*CONSTITUTIONAL LAW OF INDIA*", Allahabad Law Agency, Faridabad, 2015, pp.898

²⁴ Constitution of India, 1950

²⁵ 1968 SCR (2) 103

²⁶ Ibid.

²⁷ Article 271 of the Constitution of India, 1950

²⁸ Article 271 of the Constitution of India, 1950

²⁹ AIR 2007 SC 2990

jute products to those states, such sums as may be prescribed shall be charged on the Consolidated Fund of India in each year as grants in aid of the revenues of the states of Assam, Bihar, Orissa, and West Bengal. The sums thus stipulated shall be charged on the Consolidated Fund of India for as long as the Government of India levies an export duty on jute or jute products, or until the ten-year period from the date of the order expires.

2. Fiscal Grants Article 275 of the Constitution of India

The present Article 275 was amended by Twenty second Constitutional (Amendment) Act 1969. The Parliament is empowered to provide fiscal grants to states that are in need of financial assistance as per the President on recommendation of Finance Commission. Article 275 also provides for some specific purpose grants to meet developmental schemes for promotion and welfare of Schedule Tribe and for administration of Assam and other autonomous state as prescribed by the President of India.

4. The Union and the State have the ability to make discretionary grants in aid for certain objectives under Article 282 of the Indian Constitution of 1950. With regard to gift of aid, the term "public purpose" employed in Article 282 gives the Article a fairly broad scope. Article 282 is exempt from the Finance Commission's jurisdiction because it is discretionary and provided for special objectives. The financial planning of a state is heavily reliant on the Grants under Article 282, as this article allots a significant amount of revenue. Many centrally sponsored initiatives, such as 'UDAAN' (Udey Dish kaa aam nagrik), 'Ladli Lakshmi Yojana,' and 'Make in India,' are reliant on the grants provided under this clause. This provision empowers the Union government to make discretionary funds to the states for the purpose of achieving certain goals, such as the upliftment of scheduled classes and tribes or the provision of social services. Article 282 of the Constitution allows grants on any issue that is listed in List I, List II, or List III of the Constitution's seventh schedule. The concept of fiscal federalism is reduced in this Article since it encourages unification through these grants. The Union government frequently infringes on the autonomy of states. The concept of favouritism and nepotism in the financial relationship between the Union and the State develops as a result of the Union's unfettered discretion. As long as the ruling party at the federal level favours the same at the state level, other states in need of financial aid will be left behind. In *Bhim Singh v. U.O.I & Ors*³⁰, it was held that "both Articles 275 and 282 are sources of spending powers under the Constitution. Article 282 acts as an enabling provision to allow the Union or the State to make any grant by conferring the widest possible power."

Borrowing Power of Central and State Government

The Union government can borrow from the Consolidated Fund of India up to the prescribed amount set by Parliament, implying that the Union government has the right to raise foreign loans under List I Entry 37. The States, like the Union, have the power to borrow money, but only up to the limit set by the state legislature. States, on the other hand, cannot borrow from foreign countries; they can only borrow from the Consolidated Fund of the State within their own borders. Furthermore, the Indian government has considerable powers over state

³⁰ AIR 2010 SC 358

borrowings. The Government of India can provide a loan with a guarantee from the State Government's Consolidated Fund on behalf of the State. Before obtaining a loan from any other source, the State must first obtain authorization from the Government of India. However, such ability to raise loans or borrowings is subject to certain limitations, such as the fact that a state cannot borrow if it has already taken out a loan that has not been returned.

The Sixth Schedule area and taxing regime

Even the taxation regime in India is complicated, let alone the schedule area. With a constant struggle between the Centre and the States over who should get the lion's share of the revenue, the situation in the union territories becomes much more complicated; under these complexities, two propositions are sparingly and frequently put forward, the first being that the States are the real actors running the states, and thus they should get the lion's share of the revenue, and the second being that the Union is the machinery of the states without which the machinery of the states would not function. However, the effort to find a compromise between the two sovereign powers has yet to materialise, but in this chapter, an attempt has been made to comprehend the taxing situation in the scheduled areas, which are an important part of Indian democracy and have the potential to augment or abort India's financial growth.

Scheduled Areas

The provisions pertaining to the scheduled areas are provided for under the 6th schedule of the Indian Constitution. The 6th Schedule deals with the administration of Mizoram, Meghalaya, Tripura and Assam, seeing the sensitivity and economic structure of the area, the parts were given a special status under the Indian Constitution.

- **Assam**

A big overhaul is bound to come in the taxing regime of Assam as the GST seats at the threshold of the new financial year, it is bound to bring a change in hue of the Assam region. Under the present regime the Assam state, apart from getting its share of revenue from the Centre, also gets Grants-in-Lieu on the export duty on jute and jute products (Article 279) the amount of which is charged on the consolidated fund of India each year. The Union taxes on the Assam region can be articulately classified as follows:

- i. State Excise Duty**

The two main item of excise duty of the Assam are

- a) Alcoholic Liquors for human consumption
- b) Opium, hemp and other drugs for human consumption.

However, hemp has ceased to be a viable source of revenue as it is being regulated both at National and international level, additionally, uniform policies of the union government too are not playing a fruitful role over the deprecating revenue from the consumption of alcohol as the nationalist policy of banning liquor is just hurting the sentiments as well as burning through the pockets of the States. The seventh finance commission too had made passing by reference and had advised that the Union government must compensate the State government for the loss of revenue from the banning of liquor consumption and regulation of weed.

- ii. Assam Agriculture Income Tax Act 1939**

Apart from the liquor and hemp, agriculture has been a great source of revenue for the Assam state. The act applies both to the farm and plantation income, it is the latter which is the main source of income for the State. The agriculture sector in Assam may be broadly divided in Assam in two parts namely

- a) Plantation Sector
- b) Non-tea Plantation Sector

However, the agriculture income arising from the plantation sector has been very fluctuating and has kept the revenue of the Assam State in caprice.

iii. Land Revenue

The State government of Assam has the exclusive right to the revenue generated from the land under The Assam Land and Revenue Regulations 1886 and is of the important legislation on direct taxes in the state.

iv. GST and its effect on Assam's revenue

At the pretext of GST several changes are outpouring in the legislative arena of Assam government in order to safeguard their economic interest, which according to them is going to affect their fiscal health adversely. However, it has to be acknowledged that Assam was the first state to ratify the 122nd constitutional bill pertaining to GST, after rolling out of which sales tax, entry tax, entertainment tax and other shall be pooled under a uniform taxing structure with taxing slabs of 5, 12, 18 and 28 percent. This is an encouraging move towards a simpler tax structure as compared to the complexities of the previous system.

• Mizoram

Among other Indian States, the region of Mizoram has been quite acquainted with the concept of taxation ever since its existence, the taxes were there in the past, and the taxes are there in the present and probably in the near future as well. However, the authorities levying the taxes have changed and the sanctions behind it too have grown much more mature, previously in the pre-British era the taxes were levied by the Chiefs of the tribes/villages, in the British-India era by the British authority and now under the established suzerainty of Indian Government by the Indian Government. Some of the great revenue generators for the territory of Mizoram are as following:

i. State Excise duty

In order to fully capitalize on the market of liquor, the Mizoram Excise act was enacted in the year of 1972, however, the act remained passive for a decade long and came into force on 1984, under which taxes were levied by the state authorities on the IMFL (Indian made foreign liquor) which was the biggest source of revenue for the territory.⁸⁵ However, due to prohibition of liquor drive, the sale of liquor was banned in Mizoram with the passage of Mizoram Liquor (Total Prohibition) Act, 1995 which came into force on 20th February 1995 with the exception of three autonomous districts of Lai, Mara and Chakma.⁸⁶ However, the Fund-Striffen State Government replaced the stringent Mizoram Liquor (Total Prohibition) Act, 1995 with a much more liberal enactment of Mizoram Liquor Prohibition and Control Act 2014, recently under which the State government earned a whopping excise of 723.4 lakh.

ii. Entertainment Tax

The Assam Amusement and Betting Tax Act, 1939 extended by the Assam Autonomous District (Amusement and Betting) Regulation, 1952 was operative in Mizoram. The tax was charged on any individual, who was admitted to any entertainment institution on any entry charged.

iii. License Fees on Trading with Non-Tribals

Under the Lushai Hills (trading by Non-Tribals) Regulations, 1954, determinate fees were charged on the non-tribal who was involved in commerce with tribal of the regions. Other enacted law was specifically legislated to tax the non-tribal in the interest of the regional development.

iv. Professional Tax

Mizo District (Profession, Trades, Callings and Employment Taxation) Regulation, 1953 provided for the implication of taxes on the income of the Individuals and groups involved in the profession and employment.

Strains in Centre-State Financial Relations

The responsibility of the States, after the reform in 1991 has been increased the need of the basic services of the people. Over the years, the Centre has become more powerful in terms of revenue while the States are overburdened with more financial responsibilities. Several Commissions and Committees were appointed by the Union Government to deal with the problem in Centre-State Financial relations. The frictions between Centre and States were not resolved. These issues are as follows:

- i) **Vertical Imbalance in Resource Sharing:** The states in itself are not able to generate sufficient revenues as a result it mounts vertical imbalances. The revenue so generated by Union tax is highly elastic in nature on the other hand inelastic taxes are given to the states, which leads to a higher degree of concentration in revenue collection. For instance, the centre collects 59% of total revenue and state and local bodies collect 41 % only. The contributing areas agriculture, education, skill development, provision of health services, welfare of weaker sections etc. are in the dominion of States. As the Sixth Finance Commission observed, “When the emphasis is on social justice, there is no escape from realignment of resources in favour of States, because services and programmes which are at the core of a more equitable social order come within the purview of the States under the Constitution.”³¹
- ii) **Horizontal Imbalance:** The revenue generated by different States also differ as States differ in resources endowment, level of development and per capital income. In case of the discretionary grants provided by the centre to the states are sometimes influenced by political considerations rather than resource requirement.
- iii) **Excessive Dependence on Centre:** Indian federal structure is unique in nature under which the States are dependent upon Centre. This situation mainly emerges owing to the existence of vertical imbalance in resources source and transfer. India is a country where multi party exists. So at times there are different Parties ruling in Centre and State may not provide adequate funds to such States.

³¹ Government of India, Planning Commission Report, *Twelfth Five Year Plan (2012-17)*, Vol. II, p. 402

- iv) State Autonomy: The concept used by the framers while drafting the Constitution “strong centre and weak states” loss resulted in loss of autonomy. As post Independence there existed single party rule and State autonomy at that time completely got vanished. The increased financial dependence of States on Centre is also taking away the autonomy.
- v) **Regional Imbalances:** Since First Five Year Plan, regional imbalances were of the core concern and almost every successive plans have stressed the need to develop these areas. The Twelfth Five Year Plan, noted that the regional imbalances continue to prevail with visible gaps in production and consumption (sales), as the northern and central regions account for bulk of the exports.³² Good governance at the State level is the best way to realize the benefits of public investments.
- vi) **Growing Central Expenditure on Functions in the State List:** These are increasing discretionary transfers in the form of assistance for CSS i.e. special plan assistance and special Central assistance. The States were constrained in drawing and implementing schemes according to their priorities and the felt needs of people with growing discretionary transfers from the Centre. Since mandate is vast, the compositions of all transfers to the States are not easy to track down.
- vii) **Compliance and Enforcement Cost of Central Legislation:** The compliance and enforcement cost of the number of central legislations are entirely borne by the States, such as; the *Environment Protection Act, the Wildlife Protection Act, the Forest Conservation Act, the Biodiversity Conservation Act, the Tribal Conservation Act etc.* At present, States are not compensated for the cost loss on account of compliance. Additional costs were imposed on the States by central legislation or administrative instructions. These mainly relate to schemes of “Central Government like Sarva Siksha Abhiyan (SSA); Climate Change and Environment Management; judicial work resulting in increased case load on the courts; and fulfillment of international treaty obligations entered into by the Central Government.”
- viii) Overlapping of Functions: Where it was accepted that both Finance Commission and Planning Commission instead this relationship resulted in overlapping of functions to be performed by both the Commissions.
- ix) **Impact of Pay Revision by the Central Government on State Finances:** The periodic pay revision by the Central Government gives rise to demand on the part of State government employees for a similar pay hike. Various States have revised their pay scales and others are in the process of doing so in accordance with the recommendation of Sixth Central Pay Commission. The FC-XIV have noticed that the total expenditure of Union Government was increased in 2008-10 due to the impact of pay revision based on the recommendation of Sixth Central Pay Commission.³³ The most important recommendation of the FC-XIV is:

“We recommend the linking of pay with productivity, with a simultaneous focus on technology, skills and incentives. Further, we recommend that Pay Commissions be designated as 'Pay and Productivity Commissions', with a clear mandate to recommend

³² Government of India, Planning Commission Report, *Twelfth Five Year Plan (2012-17)*, Vol. II, p. 402

³³ Government of India, *Report of Fourteenth Finance Commission*, 2014

measures to improve 'productivity of an employee', in conjunction with pay revisions. We urge that, in future, additional remuneration be linked to increase in productivity."³⁴ So, it is desirable that with the implementation of the above mentioned recommendation, the fiscal imbalance caused due to pay revision will be reduced and a new era of strong relation will emerge.

- x) **Revision of Royalty Rates on Major Minerals:** The power to fix royalty on major minerals is vested with the Central Government. Under the provisions of the Mines and Minerals (Development and Regulation) Act, 1957, the Central Government shall not enhance the royalty in respect of any mineral more than once during any period of three years. Punchhi Commission has recommended that "the royalty rates should be revised at least every three years without any delay. States should be properly compensated for any delay in the revision of royalty beyond three years."³⁵ The revision of royalty rates affected in 2009 addressed the concerns of the States partly with regard to the conversion of specific rates into ad valorem rates on certain minerals."³⁶
- xi) **Sharing of Off-Shore Royalty and Sale Proceeds of Spectrum:** With the increased exploitation of offshore oil and gas reserves, the non-tax revenues of the Centre are likely to improve considerably through higher royalty collections. Within the parameters of present Constitutional arrangements, offshore royalty accrues entirely to the Centre. Punchhi Commission, has noticed following: "*States are largely responsible for the development of infrastructure and creating an enabling environment for the industry and business. We recommend that a part of the sale proceeds of spectrum should be devolved to the States for expenditure on infrastructure projects.*"³⁷

Judicial Pronouncements on the Fiscal Transaction between Centre and States.

In, **All India Federation of Tax practitioners v. Union of India**³⁸

The issue before the Hon'ble Supreme Court was to decide on the question of who is competent to charge service tax on Chartered Accountant and architects. It was held that tax on the service provided by the professionals will be falling under the Service Tax head. In, **D.G Gouse & co. v. State of Kerala**³⁹ A question was raised before Hon'ble Supreme Court whether tax on building will a subject matter of Centre under Entry 86 List 1 or will under the purview of wealth tax to be levied by the State legislature. It was held in this case that State of Kerala cannot impose tax as it is mere tax on building and not a wealth tax.

³⁴ Government of India, *Report of the Twelfth Finance Commission*, 2004

³⁵ Report of the Commission on Centre-State Relations (Punchhi Commission), Vol. III, 2010, p. 43

³⁶ Ibid.

³⁷ Government of India, *Report of the Commission on Centre-State Relations* (Punchhi Commission), Vol. III, 2010, p. 43

³⁸ (2007) 7 SCC 527

³⁹ AIR 1980 SC 271

In, **Man Mohan Tulli v. Delhi Corporation**⁴⁰ In the present case goods were unloaded in Delhi to be reloaded for supply in other State. The Delhi Municipal Corporation levied terminal tax on entry and exists of goods carried by road within the municipal limit. It was held that such tax is valid under Entry 56 List 2 of Schedule 7 of Constitution. In **Re Central Provinces and Berar Act no 15 of 1938**⁴¹ The Provincial tax on sale of petrol and lubricant was challenged in the present case on the ground that it is duty of excise and not sales. It was held that it is a subject of sales tax and State government is empowered to levy. In order to determine the competency of authority to impose tax the Hon'ble judiciary has evolved 'Doctrine of territorial nexus' and applied it in the services of cases. Some of those cases are **Wallace Broymers and C. v. Commissioner of Income Tax, Bombay**⁴², the territorial nexus principle was based on the decision of the present case was challenged in **Poppatlal Shah v. State of Bombay**⁴³ It was held that "*it would be quite competent to enact a legislation imposing taxes on the transactions concluded outside the province provided that there was a sufficient and real territorial nexus between such transactions and the taxing province*" The Supreme Court in **Tata Iron and Steel Company v. State of Bihar**⁴⁴ also recognized the Theory of territorial nexus. It was held in the case that "*the presence of goods at the date of agreement for the sale in the taxing state or the production or manufacturing in the state of goods the property wherein eventually passed as a result of the sale wherever it might have taken place, constituted a sufficient nexus between the taxing state and the sale*"

In **State trading corporation v. State of Mysore**⁴⁵, in the present case a company was dealing in sale of cement had made various sales of cement, which were supplied from the factories outside the state of Mysore to purchasers within the State. The State of Mysore levied tax on these sales under the two sales tax acts passed by the Mysore legislature. The company applied Art.32 of the Constitution to squash the assessment order on the ground that the State had no power to tax the sales they had taken place in the course of inter-state trade. The Court held that the sale occasions the movement of goods from one state to another within Section 3(a) of the Central Sales tax Act when the movement is the resultant of the covenant or the incident of the contract of sale. In that case, the contract of sale was deemed to have contained a covenant that the goods would be supplied in Mysore from place situated outside the borders and the sales were therefore, interstate sales within Section 3 (a) of the Central sales tax Act. In, **Escotel Mobile Communication v. Union of India**⁴⁶ A question came up before the Kerala High Court that whether Sales tax is leviable on the transaction or on part of transaction over which Sales Tax is applicable. It was held that on sale of sim card the services are provided thus both Service and Sale tax are to be leviable. Further in **Bharat Sanchar v. Union of India**⁴⁷ a wider interpretation was given regarding whether service or sales or both taxes are applicable on sale of sim card. It was held that few points are required

⁴⁰ AIR 1981 SC 991

⁴¹ AIR 1939 FC 1

⁴² AIR 1948 PC 118

⁴³ AIR 1953 SC 274

⁴⁴ AIR 1958 SC 452

⁴⁵ AIR 1963 SC 548

⁴⁶ (2002)126 STC475(ker)

⁴⁷ (2006) 3 SCC 1

to be kept in mind while imposing tax in these kinds of matters. i.e., if the sim card is not sold but was a part of service rendered by the service provider then sim cannot be taxed separately, but if purchased as a separate object then will fall under Sales Tax category.

Another matter of interpretation was came up before the Hon'ble judiciary whether a business running in different States by a dealer will be considered to be single legal entity or separate was decided in **English electric co. of India ltd v. DCTO**⁴⁸ and **Sahani steel and press work ltd v. CTO**⁴⁹, it was held that a dealer in one state having its branches at different State will be considered to be a single entity. Further question regarding levy of tax on a business in the same State was came up in **Kerala Tourism Development Corporation v. State of Kerala**⁵⁰ this question was raised while imposing tax on hotel business, as per the norms of local tax laws tax of 10% is to be levied on a turnover of 20 lakhs. The issue was each business was making turnover less than 20 lakhs but total turnover was more than 20 lakhs. It was held that business is a single legal entity and liable to pay tax. In, **ICICI Bank LTD v. Joint Commissioner sales tax, Kolkata**⁵¹, the issue raised in the present case with respect to taxing of sale and purchase by the Banking companies. It was held that although banking is not a business of sale or purchase but under Section 6 (f) of Banking Regulation Act bank other than providing banking services may indulge into "*managing, selling and realising any property which may come into the possession of the company in satisfaction or part satisfaction of any of its claims*". Thus it was held that sales tax is leviable on such transactions.

Conclusion & Suggestion

In a federation, the intergovernmental financial relationship is crucial, if not key. Modern federalism is a heartfelt notion that has a direct impact on the content and operation of a federal polity. However, creating a workable framework of inter-governmental financial relationships in a federal democracy is a difficult task, as federalism has its own set of issues. Finance is a necessary component of good governance. By looking at the Finance Body's working scheme, it is obvious that the commission has always sought to strengthen state autonomy as provided in the Indian Constitution. The Commission has devolved revenue from the Centre and distributed it to the States because the revenue generated by the States is insufficient to carry out the governance responsibilities outlined in Articles 268- 276 of the Constitution. However, there are some cases where revenue devolution from the Centre to the States is insufficient. As a result, there is a grant provision in the Indian Constitution for that purpose. A grant is a type of financial aid offered to states in need of financial support during a crisis. Furthermore, the Centre provides particular grants to States in accordance with the Indian Constitution. The particular purpose funds are used to fund development plans for Schedule Tribes' promotion and welfare. Relations between the centre and the states are complicated and have been strained in all federations, and India is no exception. In some circumstances, revenue devolution from the federal government to the states is insufficient.

⁴⁸ (1976) 4 SCC 460

⁴⁹ AIR 1985 SC 1754

⁵⁰ (2010) 27 VST 367

⁵¹ (2010) 31 VST 178

As a result, there is a grant provision in the Indian Constitution for that purpose. A grant is a type of financial aid offered to states in need of financial support during a crisis. Furthermore, the Centre provides particular grants to States in accordance with the Indian Constitution. The particular purpose funds are used to fund development plans for Schedule Tribes' promotion and welfare. Whether it was the territorial nexus theory, the interpretation of Article 282, or any other provision relating to finance under the Indian Constitution, judicial pronouncements have made a significant contribution to fiscal federalism. The sharing of revenue between the Union and the States is one of the many issues that the Court has resolved. The fight between the Centre and the State has come to an end as a result of judicial interpretations of the entries offered under Schedule 7 List I and List II. The Permanent Finance Commission should be established by amending the provisions of Constitution of India. States should be given more financial sovereignty through legislation. To improve the revenue to be disbursed, corporate income tax should be divided directly with the states. To address the issue of revenue distribution discrepancies, revenue will be dispersed according to social and economic demands. The income tax surcharge will only be imposed with the permission of the states. It is necessary for the Finance Commission and the Planning Commission to work together rather than overlap their roles. There are a number of Central laws for which the States are solely responsible for compliance and enforcement. As a result, it is desired that all future Central laws include a cost-sharing provision for the states.